

EFFECTS OF ROXARSONE ON COPPER UTILIZATION BY CHICK

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ABSTRACT

Experiment was conducted to examine the effect of dietary roxarsone (3-nitro-4-hydroxyphenylarsonic acid) on Cu utilization by chick. A fortified corn-soybean meal diet was fed to the chick. Roxarsone dramatically reduced liver Cu concentration at all levels of supplemental Cu fed. The level of roxarsone commonly fed, 50 mg/kg diet, resulted in a two-to-four fold depression in liver Cu concentration in chick. The effects of roxarsone on weight gain were more perplexity. In the chick, the diets containing 100 and 250 mg Cu/kg depressed growth in the presence, but not in the absence, of 50mg/kg dietary roxarsone. In contrast, at toxic levels of Cu, roxarsone had no effect on (500 or 750 mg Cu/kg diet) the growth-depressing effects of Cu/kg diet) the growth-depressing effects of Cu.

KEY WORDS: Roxarsone, Copper, Chick, Liver Copper, Toxicity

INTRODUCTION

Roxarsone, (3-nitro-4-hydroxyphenylarsonic acid) figure 1, is commonly used a feed additive in both poultry and susine feeds. Although the toxic effects of roxarsone have been studied (Wise *et al*; 1994; Rice *et al*; 1980), the interactions between roxarsone and another common feed additive, Cu, have not been extensively studied, using chick as model. It has been reported that roxarsone dramatically reduces liver Cu concentration in chicks fed supplemental Cu (czarnecki and Bakar, 1984). In addition, a growth depression is generally observed when growth-promoting levels of roxarsone and Cu are combined in the diet.

This study was to examine the Cu and roxarsone interaction and to determine whether it is unique for the poultry and the utilization of Cu as affected by roxarsone.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The basal diet is presented in table 1. This diet was designed to meet nutrient requirement of the chick. Supplemental roxarsone was supplied as a 10% premic and Cu as $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. All dietary additions were made at the expense of corn-starch. Feed and water were provided *ad libitum* throughout all experiments.

Broiler-type chicks were used in the experiment. The chicks were fed a corn-soybean meal starter diet during the first 7 d posthatching.

After an overnight fast, experimental groups of five male chicks were selected to have similar mean initial weight and weight distributions. Triplicate groups of five male chicks were assigned to each treatment. Assay length was 8 to 23 d post hatching and averaged initial weight was 81.7g.

The chicks were fed 0, 100, 250, 500, 750 or 1000 mg supplemental Cu/kg diet in the presence or absence of 50mg/kg supplemental roxarsone constituting a 6 x 2 factorial treatment design. Fifty milligrams/kilogram roxarsone and between 100 and 250 mg/kg Cu are the common use levels in commercial boiler production.

At the termination of the experiment, liver and bile sample were obtained per replicate. Tissues samples were dried at 100C for 24h, weighed, wet ashed with HNO₃ and analysed for Cu by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AOAC, 1984). Results are expressed as μg cu/g dry tissue.

Data were analyzed by analysis of variance, using methods appropriate for factorial treatment designs (Steel and Torrie, 1980).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the experiment are presented in figure 2 and table 2. Low levels of Cu (100 and 250mg Cu/kg diet) depressed growth in the presence, but not in the absence, of 50 mg/kg dietary roxarsone. This resulted in a roxarsone (O vs 50) x Cu (0 vs 100, 250) interaction ($p < .05$). In contrast, roxarsone slightly ameliorated ($P < .06$) the toxicity of 1,000mg Cu/kg diet, while it had had effect on the growth-depressing effect of 500 or 750mg Cu/kg diet. Liver Cu concentration was dramatically reduced by roxarsone at all levels of supplemental Cu addition ($P < .05$). Bile Cu was similarly affected.

The depression in liver Cu concentration due to feeding roxarsone was not specific for the avian species. In fact, 50mg/kg roxarsone resulted in approximately the same magnitude depression in liver Cu concentration in pig and rat (Czarnecki and Baker 1983) The roxarsone probably reduced liver Cu concentration by inhibiting Cu absorption rather than by enhancing Cu excretion.

Although, roxarsone consistently decreased liver Cu concentration at all levels of supplemental Cu intake, the effects of roxarsone on performance can be obtained from either roxarsone (50mg/kg) or Cu (100 to 250mg/kg) When fed alone, the combination produced a growth depression in chick (figure 2). Similar results were reported by Czarnecki and Baker (1984). This interaction may have important practical implications for the broiler chick. However, the combination of growth-promoting levels of roxarsone and Cu does not produce growth in pigs (Czarnecki and Baker, 1984). It is interesting and somewhat perplexing that roxarsone can either increase, decrease or have no effect on weight gain of chick fed supplemental Cu, depending on the level of Cu fed. Nonetheless, it consistently reduced liver Cu concentration.

Table 1. Composition of chick Basal Diet

Ingredient	%
Cornstarch	100
Corn meal	55.10
Soybean meal	25.08
Corn glufen meal	10.00
Corn oil	5.00
Dicalcium phosphate	2.20
Ground limestone	1.00
Iodized salt	.40
L-lysine-HCL	.25
L-Methionine	.20
Vitamin premix	.10
Choline.Cl	.10
Ferric citrate	.06
MnSO ₄	.05
ZnCO ₃	.01

Figure 1: Structure of roxarsone (3-nitro-4-hydroxyphenylarsonic acid)

Table 2. Tissue copper concentration of Chicks fed copper with or without supplemental Roxarsone^a

Copper ^b Mg/kg	Liver Copper ^c (μ g/g dry tissue)		Bile Copper ^c (μ g/g dry bile)	
	Roxarsone, mg/kg		Roxarsone, mg/kg	
	0	50	0	50
0	15.6	14.8	21.1	24.0
100	39.0	17.9	31.7	29.4
250	71.8	18.2	54.9	43.0
500	531.1	138.8	143.6	112.5
750	960.8	449.4	197.8	161.6
1,000	2,184.6	894.6	345.6	173.1

^aTissue samples from five birds within each replicate were pooled before atomic absorption analysis was performed. Pooled SE for the transformed data were .20 and .16 for liver and bile Cu, respectively.

^bprovided as $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ^cRoxarsone xCu interaction ($p < .05$).

Figure 2. Weight gain of Chicks fed graded levels of copper with or without 50mg supplemental roxarsone/kg diet.

REFERENCES

- AOAC, (1984). Official Methods of Analysis (14th Ed.) Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Washington, DC.
- Czarnecki, G. L; and Baker, D. H; (1984). Feed additive interactions in the chicken: Reduction of tissue copper deposition by dietary roxarsone in healthy and in Eimerin acevulwia-or Eimeria Tenella-infected chicks. Poul. Sci. 63:1417.
- Czarnecki, G. L; and Baker, D.H. (1983). The role of roxarsone as a metal chelating agent. Poul. Sci. 62:1407.
- Rice, D. A; McMurray, C. H; McGracken, R. M; Bryson, D. G. and Maybin, R. (1980) A field case of poisoning caused by 3-nitro-4-hydroxyphenylarsonic acid in pigs. Vet. Res. 106:312.
- Steel, R. G. D. and Torrie, J. H. (1980) Principles and procedures of statistics: A biometrical Approach (2nd Ed). McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York.
- Wise, D. R; Hartley, W. J. and Fowler, N. G; (1974). The pathology of 3-nitro-4-hydroxyphenylarsonic acid toxicity in Turkeys Res. Vet. Sci. 16:336

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